

Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples

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Abstract

*In the previous work we did **block-wise bordered** and **block-wise block-bordered** magic squares multiples of even orders. The even order multiples considered are of orders 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 22. In this case, we have blocks or block-wised bordered magic squares of equal sums. There is only two cases where we don't have equal sums is of orders 3 and 5. In case of odd order multiples, still we don't have equal sum blocks. In this situation, this work is with different block sums of magic squares resulting in a final magic squares. For examples, multiple of order 5, lead us to **block-wise bordered** magic squares of order 15, 20, 25, etc. with different sub block sums. The same is with the multiples of orders 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 and 15. Finally, we wrote **block-wise bordered** and **block-wise block-bordered** magic squares of orders 15, 20, 21, 25, 27, 28, 30, 33, 35, 36, 39, 40, 42, 44 and 45.*

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1 Introduction

In the previous works [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11], the author worked with **block-wise** constructions of magic squares. The work is from the orders 8 to 45. In each case, all the possibilities are considered. These possibilities are based on divisions of magic squares. The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \tag{1}$$

This formula is applied to all order magic squares. Based on this formula we shall bring **blocks** for the **block-wise** magic squares. That is, whenever is possible, we shall try to bring blocks of equal sum magic squares. In some cases, they are **magic**, **semi-magic**, **pandiagonal**, etc. When the question come to **bimagic** squares, in some cases, we have **semi-bimagic** squares.

On the other hand the idea of **bordered** magic squares is well explained in the work by H.White [2, 3]. Few results in this direction can be seen in author's work [12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17]. Every magic squares bigger than order 4 can always be written as **bordered** magic square. There are magic squares of type "**p**" or "**2p**", where "**p**" is a prime numbers, those can't be written as **block-wise** magic square. In this situation, they can be written as **block-bordered**, i.e., leaving external rows or columns in a uniform way, one can write them as **block-bordered**. There are few works [18, 19, 20] done by author in this direction.

The aim this work is little different, i.e., to write **block-wise bordered** and **block-wise block-bordered** magic squares. This means that instead of writing **bordered** magic square of certain orders, we shall write the **bordered** magic squares of equal parts as sub-parts of main magic square. For example, let's magic squares of order 24. It can be written as **block-wise** magic square or **bordered** magic square. Instead of writing like this, we shall write it as equal sums **sub-block bordered** magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 12. We shall call these kind of magic squares as **block-wise bordered** magic squares. This we shall do with magic squares multiples of orders 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 22. The magic squares studied are of orders 12, 16, 18, 20, 24, 28, 30, 32, 36, 40, 42 and 44.

Above we have used the terms as **block-wise**, **bordered**, **block-wise bordered**, etc. Let's rewrite again these categories:

Finally, we have written following five categories of magic squares:

- (i) **Block-Wise Magic squares**
- (ii) **Bordered Magic Squares**
- (iii) **Block-Bordered Magic Squares**
- (iv) **Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares**
- (vi) **Block-Wise Block-Bordered Magic Squares.**

More details on this terminology can be seen in author's previous work [23]. In the work [23], we have used only the **bordered** magic squares multiples of even orders. These are multiple of orders 6, 8, 10, 12, 16, 18 and 20. All the sub-blocks are of equal magic sums except for the orders 3 and 5.

In this work our aim is to work with bordered magic square multiples of even orders. The orders considers are of 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 and 15. Still, we are unable to bring equal sums blocks, i.e. we worked with **unequal sums bordered blocks** resulting in magic squares. The section below give bordered and block-bordered magic squares used in rest of the work.

2 Bordered and Block-Bordered Magic Squares

This section brings **bordered** and **block-bordered** magic squares used in rest of the work. The odd order multiples considered are of orders 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 and 15.

2.1 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 1. *The bordered magic square of order 5 is given by*

22	25	5	7	6
2	12	17	10	24
3	11	13	15	23
18	16	9	14	8
20	1	21	19	4

It is bordered magic square with magic sums: $S_{5 \times 5} := 65$ and $S_{3 \times 3} := 39$.

2.2 Magic Squares of Order 7

Example 2. *The bordered magic square of order 7 is given by*

42	38	40	5	4	2	44
1	34	37	17	19	18	49
3	14	24	29	22	36	47
43	15	23	25	27	35	7
41	30	28	21	26	20	9
39	32	13	33	31	16	11
6	12	10	45	46	48	8

It is bordered magic square with magic sums: $S_{7 \times 7} := 175$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 125$ and $S_{3 \times 3} := 75$.

Example 3. *The bordered magic square of order 7 with block of order 5 is given by*

42	38	40	5	4	2	44
1	13	19	25	31	37	49
3	30	36	17	18	24	47
43	22	23	29	35	16	7
41	34	15	21	27	28	9
39	26	32	33	14	20	11
6	12	10	45	46	48	8

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 7 with *pandiagonal* block of order 5. The magic sums are $S_{7 \times 7} := 175$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := 125$.

2.3 Magic Squares of Order 9

Example 4. The *bordered* magic square of order 9 is given by

8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10
1	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	81
3	17	50	53	33	35	34	65	79
5	19	30	40	45	38	52	63	77
73	59	31	39	41	43	51	23	9
71	57	46	44	37	42	36	25	11
69	55	48	29	49	47	32	27	13
67	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	15
72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74

It is *bordered* magic square with magic sums: $S_{9 \times 9} := 369$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 287$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 205$ and $S_{3 \times 3} := 123$.

Example 5. The *bordered* magic square of order 9 with block of order 7 is given by

8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10
1	17	25	33	41	49	57	65	81
3	56	64	23	24	32	40	48	79
5	39	47	55	63	22	30	31	77
73	29	37	38	46	54	62	21	9
71	61	20	28	36	44	45	53	11
69	51	52	60	19	27	35	43	13
67	34	42	50	58	59	18	26	15
72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 9 with *pandiagonal* block of order 7. The magic sums are $S_{9 \times 9} := 369$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := 287$.

2.4 Magic Squares of Order 11

Example 6. The *bordered* magic square of order 11 is given by

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10
121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1
119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3
117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5
115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7
11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111
13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109
15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107
17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105
19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110

It is *bordered* magic square with magic sums: $S_{11 \times 11} := 671$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 549$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 427$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 305$ and $S_{3 \times 3} := 123$.

Example 7. The *bordered* magic square of order 11 with block of order 7 is given by

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10
121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1
119	21	37	45	53	61	69	77	85	101	3
117	23	76	84	43	44	52	60	68	99	5
115	25	59	67	75	83	42	50	51	97	7
11	93	49	57	58	66	74	82	41	29	111
13	91	81	40	48	56	64	65	73	31	109
15	89	71	72	80	39	47	55	63	33	107
17	87	54	62	70	78	79	38	46	35	105
19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 11 with *pandiagonal* block of order 7. The magic sums are $S_{11 \times 11} := 671$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 549$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := 427$.

Example 8. The *bordered* magic square of order 11 with blocks of order 3 is given by

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10
121	21	33	45	50	62	74	76	88	100	1
119	49	61	73	75	87	99	23	35	47	3
117	77	89	101	22	34	46	48	60	72	5
115	42	27	30	71	56	59	97	82	85	7
11	70	55	58	96	81	84	44	29	32	111
13	98	83	86	43	28	31	69	54	57	109
15	36	39	24	65	68	53	91	94	79	107
17	64	67	52	90	93	78	38	41	26	105
19	92	95	80	37	40	25	63	66	51	103
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 11 with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 9. It is composed of 9 blocks of *semi-magic* squares with equal *semi-magic* sums. The magic sums are $S_{11 \times 11} := 671$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 549$ and $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := 183$.

Example 9. The bordered magic square of order 11 with blocks of order 3 is given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	45	62	67	79	84	92	104	109	123	25	166
6	143	77	82	96	99	116	121	52	57	65	27	164
8	141	106	111	119	50	55	69	72	89	94	29	162
10	139	71	49	54	93	74	88	118	105	113	31	160
11	35	91	78	86	125	103	108	66	47	61	135	159
154	37	120	101	115	64	51	59	98	76	81	133	16
152	39	58	63	53	83	97	75	114	122	100	131	18
150	41	87	95	73	112	117	107	56	70	48	129	20
148	43	110	124	102	60	68	46	85	90	80	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 11 with *bimagic* square of order 9. It is composed of 9 blocks of order 3. The sums of 9 entries of each block of order 3 is same as of magic square of order 9. The magic sums are $S_{11 \times 11} := 671$, and $S_{9 \times 9} := 549$.

2.5 Magic Squares of Order 13

Example 10. The bordered magic square of order 13 is given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	25	166
6	143	45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	27	164
8	141	47	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	123	29	162
10	139	49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	31	160
11	35	117	103	75	83	85	87	95	67	53	135	159
154	37	115	101	90	88	81	86	80	69	55	133	16
152	39	113	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	57	131	18
150	41	111	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	59	129	20
148	43	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

It is *bordered* magic square with magic sums: $S_{13 \times 13} := 1105$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 935$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 765$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 595$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 425$ and $S_{3 \times 3} := 255$.

Example 11. The *bordered* magic square of order 13 with block of order 7 is given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	25	166
6	143	45	61	69	77	85	93	101	109	125	27	164
8	141	47	100	108	67	68	76	84	92	123	29	162
10	139	49	83	91	99	107	66	74	75	121	31	160
11	35	117	73	81	82	90	98	106	65	53	135	159
154	37	115	105	64	72	80	88	89	97	55	133	16
152	39	113	95	96	104	63	71	79	87	57	131	18
150	41	111	78	86	94	102	103	62	70	59	129	20
148	43	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

It is **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 with **pandiagonal** block of order 7. The magic sums are $S_{13 \times 13} := 1105$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 935$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 765$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := 595$.

Example 12. The **bordered** magic square of order 13 with blocks of order 3 is given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	45	57	69	74	86	98	100	112	124	25	166
6	143	73	85	97	99	111	123	47	59	71	27	164
8	141	101	113	125	46	58	70	72	84	96	29	162
10	139	66	51	54	95	80	83	121	106	109	31	160
11	35	94	79	82	120	105	108	68	53	56	135	159
154	37	122	107	110	67	52	55	93	78	81	133	16
152	39	60	63	48	89	92	77	115	118	103	131	18
150	41	88	91	76	114	117	102	62	65	50	129	20
148	43	116	119	104	61	64	49	87	90	75	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 13 with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 9. It is composed of 9 blocks of *semi-magic* squares with equal *semi-magic* sums. The magic sums are $S_{13 \times 13} := 1105$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 935$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 765$ and $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := 255$.

Example 13. The *bordered* magic square of order 13 with blocks of order 3 is given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	45	62	67	79	84	92	104	109	123	25	166
6	143	77	82	96	99	116	121	52	57	65	27	164
8	141	106	111	119	50	55	69	72	89	94	29	162
10	139	71	49	54	93	74	88	118	105	113	31	160
11	35	91	78	86	125	103	108	66	47	61	135	159
154	37	120	101	115	64	51	59	98	76	81	133	16
152	39	58	63	53	83	97	75	114	122	100	131	18
150	41	87	95	73	112	117	107	56	70	48	129	20
148	43	110	124	102	60	68	46	85	90	80	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 13 with *bimagic* square of order 9. It is composed of 9 blocks of order 3. The sums of 9 entries of each block of order 3 is same as of magic square of order 9. The magic sums are $S_{13 \times 13} := 1105$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 935$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := 765$.

2.6 Magic Squares of Order 15

Example 14. The *bordered* magic square of order 15 is given by

210	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	11	9	7	5	3	1	14
2	184	175	177	179	181	183	185	37	35	33	31	29	40	224
4	30	64	72	70	68	66	165	166	168	170	172	62	196	222
6	32	173	80	152	150	148	147	84	86	88	82	53	194	220
8	34	171	73	130	126	128	93	92	90	132	153	55	192	218
10	36	169	75	89	122	125	105	107	106	137	151	57	190	216
12	38	167	77	91	102	112	117	110	124	135	149	59	188	214
13	39	63	145	131	103	111	113	115	123	95	81	163	187	213
208	182	65	143	129	118	116	109	114	108	97	83	161	44	18
206	180	67	141	127	120	101	121	119	104	99	85	159	46	20
204	178	69	139	94	100	98	133	134	136	96	87	157	48	22
202	176	71	144	74	76	78	79	142	140	138	146	155	50	24
200	174	164	154	156	158	160	61	60	58	56	54	162	52	26
198	186	51	49	47	45	43	41	189	191	193	195	197	42	28
212	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	215	217	219	221	223	225	16

It is *bordered* magic square of order 15 with magic sums: $S_{15 \times 15} := 1695$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 1469$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 1243$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1017$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 791$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 565$ and $S_{3 \times 3} := 339$.

Example 15. The *bordered* magic square of order 15 with block of order 7 is given by

210	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	11	9	7	5	3	1	14
2	184	175	177	179	181	183	185	37	35	33	31	29	40	224
4	30	64	72	70	68	66	165	166	168	170	172	62	196	222
6	32	173	80	152	150	148	147	84	86	88	82	53	194	220
8	34	171	73	89	97	105	113	121	129	137	153	55	192	218
10	36	169	75	128	136	95	96	104	112	120	151	57	190	216
12	38	167	77	111	119	127	135	94	102	103	149	59	188	214
13	39	63	145	101	109	110	118	126	134	93	81	163	187	213
208	182	65	143	133	92	100	108	116	117	125	83	161	44	18
206	180	67	141	123	124	132	91	99	107	115	85	159	46	20
204	178	69	139	106	114	122	130	131	90	98	87	157	48	22
202	176	71	144	74	76	78	79	142	140	138	146	155	50	24
200	174	164	154	156	158	160	61	60	58	56	54	162	52	26
198	186	51	49	47	45	43	41	189	191	193	195	197	42	28
212	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	215	217	219	221	223	225	16

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 15 with *pandiagonal* block of order 7. The magic sums are $S_{15 \times 15} := 1695$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 1469$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 1243$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1017$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := 791$.

Example 16. The *bordered* magic square of order 15 with blocks of order 3 is given by

210	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	11	9	7	5	3	1	14
2	184	175	177	179	181	183	185	37	35	33	31	29	40	224
4	30	64	72	70	68	66	165	166	168	170	172	62	196	222
6	32	173	73	85	97	102	114	126	128	140	152	53	194	220
8	34	171	101	113	125	127	139	151	75	87	99	55	192	218
10	36	169	129	141	153	74	86	98	100	112	124	57	190	216
12	38	167	94	79	82	123	108	111	149	134	137	59	188	214
13	39	63	122	107	110	148	133	136	96	81	84	163	187	213
208	182	65	150	135	138	95	80	83	121	106	109	161	44	18
206	180	67	88	91	76	117	120	105	143	146	131	159	46	20
204	178	69	116	119	104	142	145	130	90	93	78	157	48	22
202	176	71	144	147	132	89	92	77	115	118	103	155	50	24
200	174	164	154	156	158	160	61	60	58	56	54	162	52	26
198	186	51	49	47	45	43	41	189	191	193	195	197	42	28
212	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	215	217	219	221	223	225	16

It is *block-bordered* magic square of order 15 with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 9. It is composed of 9 blocks of *semi-magic* squares with equal *semi-magic* sums. The magic sums are $S_{15 \times 15} := 1695$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 1469$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 1243$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1017$ and $S_{3 \times 3} := 424$.

Example 17. The *bordered* magic square of order 15 with blocks of order 3 is given by

210	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	11	9	7	5	3	1	14
2	184	175	177	179	181	183	185	37	35	33	31	29	40	224
4	30	64	72	70	68	66	165	166	168	170	172	62	196	222
6	32	173	73	90	95	107	112	120	132	137	151	53	194	220
8	34	171	105	110	124	127	144	149	80	85	93	55	192	218
10	36	169	134	139	147	78	83	97	100	117	122	57	190	216
12	38	167	99	77	82	121	102	116	146	133	141	59	188	214
13	39	63	119	106	114	153	131	136	94	75	89	163	187	213
208	182	65	148	129	143	92	79	87	126	104	109	161	44	18
206	180	67	86	91	81	111	125	103	142	150	128	159	46	20
204	178	69	115	123	101	140	145	135	84	98	76	157	48	22
202	176	71	138	152	130	88	96	74	113	118	108	155	50	24
200	174	164	154	156	158	160	61	60	58	56	54	162	52	26
198	186	51	49	47	45	43	41	189	191	193	195	197	42	28
212	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	215	217	219	221	223	225	16

It is **block-bordered** magic square of order 15 with **bimagic** square of order 9. It is composed of 9 blocks of order 3. The sums of 9 entries of each block of order 3 is same as of magic square of order 9. The magic sums are $S_{15 \times 15} := 1695$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 1469$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 1243$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := 1017$.

The section below give **block-wise bordered** magic squares multiples of above magic squares.

3 Block-Wise Bordered and Block-Bordered Magic Squares

3.1 Magic Square of Order 15

In this case we shall used **bordered** magic square of order 5 given in Example 1 to write **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 15

Example 18. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 15 is given by*

97	100	80	82	81	222	225	205	207	206	47	50	30	32	31
77	87	92	85	99	202	212	217	210	224	27	37	42	35	49
78	86	88	90	98	203	211	213	215	223	28	36	38	40	48
93	91	84	89	83	218	216	209	214	208	43	41	34	39	33
95	76	96	94	79	220	201	221	219	204	45	26	46	44	29
72	75	55	57	56	122	125	105	107	106	172	175	155	157	156
52	62	67	60	74	102	112	117	110	124	152	162	167	160	174
53	61	63	65	73	103	111	113	115	123	153	161	163	165	173
68	66	59	64	58	118	116	109	114	108	168	166	159	164	158
70	51	71	69	54	120	101	121	119	104	170	151	171	169	154
197	200	180	182	181	22	25	5	7	6	147	150	130	132	131
177	187	192	185	199	2	12	17	10	24	127	137	142	135	149
178	186	188	190	198	3	11	13	15	23	128	136	138	140	148
193	191	184	189	183	18	16	9	14	8	143	141	134	139	133
195	176	196	194	179	20	1	21	19	4	145	126	146	144	129

It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 5 with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{15 \times 15} := 1695$.

3.2 Magic Square of Order 20

In this case we shall use **bordered** magic square of order 5 given in Example 1 to write **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 20.

Example 19. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 20 is given by*

97	100	80	82	81	222	225	205	207	206	47	50	30	32	31
77	87	92	85	99	202	212	217	210	224	27	37	42	35	49
78	86	88	90	98	203	211	213	215	223	28	36	38	40	48
93	91	84	89	83	218	216	209	214	208	43	41	34	39	33
95	76	96	94	79	220	201	221	219	204	45	26	46	44	29
72	75	55	57	56	122	125	105	107	106	172	175	155	157	156
52	62	67	60	74	102	112	117	110	124	152	162	167	160	174
53	61	63	65	73	103	111	113	115	123	153	161	163	165	173
68	66	59	64	58	118	116	109	114	108	168	166	159	164	158
70	51	71	69	54	120	101	121	119	104	170	151	171	169	154
197	200	180	182	181	22	25	5	7	6	147	150	130	132	131
177	187	192	185	199	2	12	17	10	24	127	137	142	135	149
178	186	188	190	198	3	11	13	15	23	128	136	138	140	148
193	191	184	189	183	18	16	9	14	8	143	141	134	139	133
195	176	196	194	179	20	1	21	19	4	145	126	146	144	129

It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 5 with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{20 \times 20} := 4010$.

3.3 Magic Squares of Order 21

In this case we shall use **bordered** and **block-bordered** magic squares of order 7 given in Examples 2 and 3 to write **block-wise bordered** magic squares of order 21.

Example 20. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 21 is given by*

189	185	187	152	151	149	191	434	430	432	397	396	394	436	91	87	89	54	53	51	93
148	181	184	164	166	165	196	393	426	429	409	411	410	441	50	83	86	66	68	67	98
150	161	171	176	169	183	194	395	406	416	421	414	428	439	52	63	73	78	71	85	96
190	162	170	172	174	182	154	435	407	415	417	419	427	399	92	64	72	74	76	84	56
188	177	175	168	173	167	156	433	422	420	413	418	412	401	90	79	77	70	75	69	58
186	179	160	180	178	163	158	431	424	405	425	423	408	403	88	81	62	82	80	65	60
153	159	157	192	193	195	155	398	404	402	437	438	440	400	55	61	59	94	95	97	57
140	136	138	103	102	100	142	238	234	236	201	200	198	240	336	332	334	299	298	296	338
99	132	135	115	117	116	147	197	230	233	213	215	214	245	295	328	331	311	313	312	343
101	112	122	127	120	134	145	199	210	220	225	218	232	243	297	308	318	323	316	330	341
141	113	121	123	125	133	105	239	211	219	221	223	231	203	337	309	317	319	321	329	301
139	128	126	119	124	118	107	237	226	224	217	222	216	205	335	324	322	315	320	314	303
137	130	111	131	129	114	109	235	228	209	229	227	212	207	333	326	307	327	325	310	305
104	110	108	143	144	146	106	202	208	206	241	242	244	204	300	306	304	339	340	342	302
385	381	383	348	347	345	387	42	38	40	5	4	2	44	287	283	285	250	249	247	289
344	377	380	360	362	361	392	1	34	37	17	19	18	49	246	279	282	262	264	263	294
346	357	367	372	365	379	390	3	14	24	29	22	36	47	248	259	269	274	267	281	292
386	358	366	368	370	378	350	43	15	23	25	27	35	7	288	260	268	270	272	280	252
384	373	371	364	369	363	352	41	30	28	21	26	20	9	286	275	273	266	271	265	254
382	375	356	376	374	359	354	39	32	13	33	31	16	11	284	277	258	278	276	261	256
349	355	353	388	389	391	351	6	12	10	45	46	48	8	251	257	255	290	291	293	253

It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 7 with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{21 \times 21} := 4641$

Example 21. *block-wise block-bordered* magic square of order 21 with inner block of order 5 is given by

189	185	187	152	151	149	191	434	430	432	397	396	394	436	91	87	89	54	53	51	93
148	160	166	172	178	184	196	393	405	411	417	423	429	441	50	62	68	74	80	86	98
150	177	183	164	165	171	194	395	422	428	409	410	416	439	52	79	85	66	67	73	96
190	169	170	176	182	163	154	435	414	415	421	427	408	399	92	71	72	78	84	65	56
188	181	162	168	174	175	156	433	426	407	413	419	420	401	90	83	64	70	76	77	58
186	173	179	180	161	167	158	431	418	424	425	406	412	403	88	75	81	82	63	69	60
153	159	157	192	193	195	155	398	404	402	437	438	440	400	55	61	59	94	95	97	57
140	136	138	103	102	100	142	238	234	236	201	200	198	240	336	332	334	299	298	296	338
99	111	117	123	129	135	147	197	209	215	221	227	233	245	295	307	313	319	325	331	343
101	128	134	115	116	122	145	199	226	232	213	214	220	243	297	324	330	311	312	318	341
141	120	121	127	133	114	105	239	218	219	225	231	212	203	337	316	317	323	329	310	301
139	132	113	119	125	126	107	237	230	211	217	223	224	205	335	328	309	315	321	322	303
137	124	130	131	112	118	109	235	222	228	229	210	216	207	333	320	326	327	308	314	305
104	110	108	143	144	146	106	202	208	206	241	242	244	204	300	306	304	339	340	342	302
385	381	383	348	347	345	387	42	38	40	5	4	2	44	287	283	285	250	249	247	289
344	356	362	368	374	380	392	1	13	19	25	31	37	49	246	258	264	270	276	282	294
346	373	379	360	361	367	390	3	30	36	17	18	24	47	248	275	281	262	263	269	292
386	365	366	372	378	359	350	43	22	23	29	35	16	7	288	267	268	274	280	261	252
384	377	358	364	370	371	352	41	34	15	21	27	28	9	286	279	260	266	272	273	254
382	369	375	376	357	363	354	39	26	32	33	14	20	11	284	271	277	278	259	265	256
349	355	353	388	389	391	351	6	12	10	45	46	48	8	251	257	255	290	291	293	253

It is formed by blocks of *bordered* magic squares of order 7 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 5 are *pandiagonal* with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{21 \times 21} := 4641$.

3.4 Magic Square of Order 25

In this case we shall use *bordered* magic square of order 5 given in Example 1 to write *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 25.

Example 22. *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 25 is given by

22	25	5	7	6	172	175	155	157	156	322	325	305	307	306	472	475	455	457	456	622	625	605	607	606
2	12	17	10	24	152	162	167	160	174	302	312	317	310	324	452	462	467	460	474	602	612	617	610	624
3	11	13	15	23	153	161	163	165	173	303	311	313	315	323	453	461	463	465	473	603	611	613	615	623
18	16	9	14	8	168	166	159	164	158	318	316	309	314	308	468	466	459	464	458	618	616	609	614	608
20	1	21	19	4	170	151	171	169	154	320	301	321	319	304	470	451	471	469	454	620	601	621	619	604
447	450	430	432	431	597	600	580	582	581	122	125	105	107	106	147	150	130	132	131	297	300	280	282	281
427	437	442	435	449	577	587	592	585	599	102	112	117	110	124	127	137	142	135	149	277	287	292	285	299
428	436	438	440	448	578	586	588	590	598	103	111	113	115	123	128	136	138	140	148	278	286	288	290	298
443	441	434	439	433	593	591	584	589	583	118	116	109	114	108	143	141	134	139	133	293	291	284	289	283
445	426	446	444	429	595	576	596	594	579	120	101	121	119	104	145	126	146	144	129	295	276	296	294	279
247	250	230	232	231	272	275	255	257	256	422	425	405	407	406	572	575	555	557	556	97	100	80	82	81
227	237	242	235	249	252	262	267	260	274	402	412	417	410	424	552	562	567	560	574	77	87	92	85	99
228	236	238	240	248	253	261	263	265	273	403	411	413	415	423	553	561	563	565	573	78	86	88	90	98
243	241	234	239	233	268	266	259	264	258	418	416	409	414	408	568	566	559	564	558	93	91	84	89	83
245	226	246	244	229	270	251	271	269	254	420	401	421	419	404	570	551	571	569	554	95	76	96	94	79
547	550	530	532	531	72	75	55	57	56	222	225	205	207	206	372	375	355	357	356	397	400	380	382	381
527	537	542	535	549	52	62	67	60	74	202	212	217	210	224	352	362	367	360	374	377	387	392	385	399
528	536	538	540	548	53	61	63	65	73	203	211	213	215	223	353	361	363	365	373	378	386	388	390	398
543	541	534	539	533	68	66	59	64	58	218	216	209	214	208	368	366	359	364	358	393	391	384	389	383
545	526	546	544	529	70	51	71	69	54	220	201	221	219	204	370	351	371	369	354	395	376	396	394	379
347	350	330	332	331	497	500	480	482	481	522	525	505	507	506	47	50	30	32	31	197	200	180	182	181
327	337	342	335	349	477	487	492	485	499	502	512	517	510	524	27	37	42	35	49	177	187	192	185	199
328	336	338	340	348	478	486	488	490	498	503	511	513	515	523	28	36	38	40	48	178	186	188	190	198
343	341	334	339	333	493	491	484	489	483	518	516	509	514	508	43	41	34	39	33	193	191	184	189	183
345	326	346	344	329	495	476	496	494	479	520	501	521	519	504	45	26	46	44	29	195	176	196	194	179

It is formed by blocks of bordered magic squares of order 5 with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{25 \times 25} := 7825$.

3.5 Magic Squares of Order 27

In this case we shall use bordered magic squares of order 9 given in Examples 4 and 5 to write block-wise bordered magic square of order 27.

Example 23. block-wise bordered magic square of order 27 is given by

251	323	321	319	318	255	257	259	253	656	728	726	724	723	660	662	664	658	89	161	159	157	156	93	95	97	91
244	301	297	299	264	263	261	303	324	649	706	702	704	669	668	666	708	729	82	139	135	137	102	101	99	141	162
246	260	293	296	276	278	277	308	322	651	665	698	701	681	683	682	713	727	84	98	131	134	114	116	115	146	160
248	262	273	283	288	281	295	306	320	653	667	678	688	693	686	700	711	725	86	100	111	121	126	119	133	144	158
316	302	274	282	284	286	294	266	252	721	707	679	687	689	691	699	671	657	154	140	112	120	122	124	132	104	90
314	300	289	287	280	285	279	268	254	719	705	694	692	685	690	684	673	659	152	138	127	125	118	123	117	106	92
312	298	291	272	292	290	275	270	256	717	703	696	677	697	695	680	675	661	150	136	129	110	130	128	113	108	94
310	265	271	269	304	305	307	267	258	715	670	676	674	709	710	712	672	663	148	103	109	107	142	143	145	105	96
315	245	247	249	250	313	311	309	317	720	650	652	654	655	718	716	714	722	153	83	85	87	88	151	149	147	155
170	242	240	238	237	174	176	178	172	332	404	402	400	399	336	338	340	334	494	566	564	562	561	498	500	502	496
163	220	216	218	183	182	180	222	243	325	382	378	380	345	344	342	384	405	487	544	540	542	507	506	504	546	567
165	179	212	215	195	197	196	227	241	327	341	374	377	357	359	358	389	403	489	503	536	539	519	521	520	551	565
167	181	192	202	207	200	214	225	239	329	343	354	364	369	362	376	387	401	491	505	516	526	531	524	538	549	563
235	221	193	201	203	205	213	185	171	397	383	355	363	365	367	375	347	333	559	545	517	525	527	529	537	509	495
233	219	208	206	199	204	198	187	173	395	381	370	368	361	366	360	349	335	557	543	532	530	523	528	522	511	497
231	217	210	191	211	209	194	189	175	393	379	372	353	373	371	356	351	337	555	541	534	515	535	533	518	513	499
229	184	190	188	223	224	226	186	177	391	346	352	350	385	386	388	348	339	553	508	514	512	547	548	550	510	501
234	164	166	168	169	232	230	228	236	396	326	328	330	331	394	392	390	398	558	488	490	492	493	556	554	552	560
575	647	645	643	642	579	581	583	577	8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	413	485	483	481	480	417	419	421	415
568	625	621	623	588	587	585	627	648	1	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	81	406	463	459	461	426	425	423	465	486
570	584	617	620	600	602	601	632	646	3	17	50	53	33	35	34	65	79	408	422	455	458	438	440	439	470	484
572	586	597	607	612	605	619	630	644	5	19	30	40	45	38	52	63	77	410	424	435	445	450	443	457	468	482
640	626	598	606	608	610	618	590	576	73	59	31	39	41	43	51	23	9	478	464	436	444	446	448	456	428	414
638	624	613	611	604	609	603	592	578	71	57	46	44	37	42	36	25	11	476	462	451	449	442	447	441	430	416
636	622	615	596	616	614	599	594	580	69	55	48	29	49	47	32	27	13	474	460	453	434	454	452	437	432	418
634	589	595	593	628	629	631	591	582	67	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	15	472	427	433	431	466	467	469	429	420
639	569	571	573	574	637	635	633	641	72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	477	407	409	411	412	475	473	471	479

It is formed by blocks of bordered magic squares of order 9 with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{27 \times 27} := 9855$.

Example 24. block-wise bordered magic square of order 27 of is given by

251	323	321	319	318	255	257	259	253	656	728	726	724	723	660	662	664	658	89	161	159	157	156	93	95	97	91
244	260	268	276	284	292	300	308	324	649	665	673	681	689	697	705	713	729	82	98	106	114	122	130	138	146	162
246	299	307	266	267	275	283	291	322	651	704	712	671	672	680	688	696	727	84	137	145	104	105	113	121	129	160
248	282	290	298	306	265	273	274	320	653	687	695	703	711	670	678	679	725	86	120	128	136	144	103	111	112	158
316	272	280	281	289	297	305	264	252	721	677	685	686	694	702	710	669	657	154	110	118	119	127	135	143	102	90
314	304	263	271	279	287	288	296	254	719	709	668	676	684	692	693	701	659	152	142	101	109	117	125	126	134	92
312	294	295	303	262	270	278	286	256	717	699	700	708	667	675	683	691	661	150	132	133	141	100	108	116	124	94
310	277	285	293	301	302	261	269	258	715	682	690	698	706	707	666	674	663	148	115	123	131	139	140	99	107	96
315	245	247	249	250	313	311	309	317	720	650	652	654	655	718	716	714	722	153	83	85	87	88	151	149	147	155
170	242	240	238	237	174	176	178	172	332	404	402	400	399	336	338	340	334	494	566	564	562	561	498	500	502	496
163	179	187	195	203	211	219	227	243	325	341	349	357	365	373	381	389	405	487	503	511	519	527	535	543	551	567
165	218	226	185	186	194	202	210	241	327	380	388	347	348	356	364	372	403	489	542	550	509	510	518	526	534	565
167	201	209	217	225	184	192	193	239	329	363	371	379	387	346	354	355	401	491	525	533	541	549	508	516	517	563
235	191	199	200	208	216	224	183	171	397	353	361	362	370	378	386	345	333	559	515	523	524	532	540	548	507	495
233	223	182	190	198	206	207	215	173	395	385	344	352	360	368	369	377	335	557	547	506	514	522	530	531	539	497
231	213	214	222	181	189	197	205	175	393	375	376	384	343	351	359	367	337	555	537	538	546	505	513	521	529	499
229	196	204	212	220	221	180	188	177	391	358	366	374	382	383	342	350	339	553	520	528	536	544	545	504	512	501
234	164	166	168	169	232	230	228	236	396	326	328	330	331	394	392	390	398	558	488	490	492	493	556	554	552	560
575	647	645	643	642	579	581	583	577	8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	413	485	483	481	480	417	419	421	415
568	584	592	600	608	616	624	632	648	1	17	25	33	41	49	57	65	81	406	422	430	438	446	454	462	470	486
570	623	631	590	591	599	607	615	646	3	56	64	23	24	32	40	48	79	408	461	469	428	429	437	445	453	484
572	606	614	622	630	589	597	598	644	5	39	47	55	63	22	30	31	77	410	444	452	460	468	427	435	436	482
640	596	604	605	613	621	629	588	576	73	29	37	38	46	54	62	21	9	478	434	442	443	451	459	467	426	414
638	628	587	595	603	611	612	620	578	71	61	20	28	36	44	45	53	11	476	466	425	433	441	449	450	458	416
636	618	619	627	586	594	602	610	580	69	51	52	60	19	27	35	43	13	474	456	457	465	424	432	440	448	418
634	601	609	617	625	626	585	593	582	67	34	42	50	58	59	18	26	15	472	439	447	455	463	464	423	431	420
639	569	571	573	574	637	635	633	641	72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	477	407	409	411	412	475	473	471	479

It is formed by blocks of *bordered* magic squares of order 9 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 7 are *pandiagonal* with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{27 \times 27} := 9855$.

3.6 Magic Squares of Order 28

In this case we shall use *bordered* magic squares of order 7 given in Examples 2 and 3 to write *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 28.

Example 25. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 28 is given by*

336	332	334	299	298	296	338	581	577	579	544	543	541	583	42	38	40	5	4	2	44	679	675	677	642	641	639	681
295	328	331	311	313	312	343	540	573	576	556	558	557	588	1	34	37	17	19	18	49	638	671	674	654	656	655	686
297	308	318	323	316	330	341	542	553	563	568	561	575	586	3	14	24	29	22	36	47	640	651	661	666	659	673	684
337	309	317	319	321	329	301	582	554	562	564	566	574	546	43	15	23	25	27	35	7	680	652	660	662	664	672	644
335	324	322	315	320	314	303	580	569	567	560	565	559	548	41	30	28	21	26	20	9	678	667	665	658	663	657	646
333	326	307	327	325	310	305	578	571	552	572	570	555	550	39	32	13	33	31	16	11	676	669	650	670	668	653	648
300	306	304	339	340	342	302	545	551	549	584	585	587	547	6	12	10	45	46	48	8	643	649	647	682	683	685	645
91	87	89	54	53	51	93	630	626	628	593	592	590	632	385	381	383	348	347	345	387	532	528	530	495	494	492	534
50	83	86	66	68	67	98	589	622	625	605	607	606	637	344	377	380	360	362	361	392	491	524	527	507	509	508	539
52	63	73	78	71	85	96	591	602	612	617	610	624	635	346	357	367	372	365	379	390	493	504	514	519	512	526	537
92	64	72	74	76	84	56	631	603	611	613	615	623	595	386	358	366	368	370	378	350	533	505	513	515	517	525	497
90	79	77	70	75	69	58	629	618	616	609	614	608	597	384	373	371	364	369	363	352	531	520	518	511	516	510	499
88	81	62	82	80	65	60	627	620	601	621	619	604	599	382	375	356	376	374	359	354	529	522	503	523	521	506	501
55	61	59	94	95	97	57	594	600	598	633	634	636	596	349	355	353	388	389	391	351	496	502	500	535	536	538	498
777	773	775	740	739	737	779	140	136	138	103	102	100	142	483	479	481	446	445	443	485	238	234	236	201	200	198	240
736	769	772	752	754	753	784	99	132	135	115	117	116	147	442	475	478	458	460	459	490	197	230	233	213	215	214	245
738	749	759	764	757	771	782	101	112	122	127	120	134	145	444	455	465	470	463	477	488	199	210	220	225	218	232	243
778	750	758	760	762	770	742	141	113	121	123	125	133	105	484	456	464	466	468	476	448	239	211	219	221	223	231	203
776	765	763	756	761	755	744	139	128	126	119	124	118	107	482	471	469	462	467	461	450	237	226	224	217	222	216	205
774	767	748	768	766	751	746	137	130	111	131	129	114	109	480	473	454	474	472	457	452	235	228	209	229	227	212	207
741	747	745	780	781	783	743	104	110	108	143	144	146	106	447	453	451	486	487	489	449	202	208	206	241	242	244	204
434	430	432	397	396	394	436	287	283	285	250	249	247	289	728	724	726	691	690	688	730	189	185	187	152	151	149	191
393	426	429	409	411	410	441	246	279	282	262	264	263	294	687	720	723	703	705	704	735	148	181	184	164	166	165	196
395	406	416	421	414	428	439	248	259	269	274	267	281	292	689	700	710	715	708	722	733	150	161	171	176	169	183	194
435	407	415	417	419	427	399	288	260	268	270	272	280	252	729	701	709	711	713	721	693	190	162	170	172	174	182	154
433	422	420	413	418	412	401	286	275	273	266	271	265	254	727	716	714	707	712	706	695	188	177	175	168	173	167	156
431	424	405	425	423	408	403	284	277	258	278	276	261	256	725	718	699	719	717	702	697	186	179	160	180	178	163	158
398	404	402	437	438	440	400	251	257	255	290	291	293	253	692	698	696	731	732	734	694	153	159	157	192	193	195	155

It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 7 with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{28 \times 28} := 10990$.

Example 26. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 28 of is given by*

336	332	334	299	298	296	338	581	577	579	544	543	541	583	42	38	40	5	4	2	44	679	675	677	642	641	639	681
295	307	313	319	325	331	343	540	552	558	564	570	576	588	1	13	19	25	31	37	49	638	650	656	662	668	674	686
297	324	330	311	312	318	341	542	569	575	556	557	563	586	3	30	36	17	18	24	47	640	667	673	654	655	661	684
337	316	317	323	329	310	301	582	561	562	568	574	555	546	43	22	23	29	35	16	7	680	659	660	666	672	653	644
335	328	309	315	321	322	303	580	573	554	560	566	567	548	41	34	15	21	27	28	9	678	671	652	658	664	665	646
333	320	326	327	308	314	305	578	565	571	572	553	559	550	39	26	32	33	14	20	11	676	663	669	670	651	657	648
300	306	304	339	340	342	302	545	551	549	584	585	587	547	6	12	10	45	46	48	8	643	649	647	682	683	685	645
91	87	89	54	53	51	93	630	626	628	593	592	590	632	385	381	383	348	347	345	387	532	528	530	495	494	492	534
50	62	68	74	80	86	98	589	601	607	613	619	625	637	344	356	362	368	374	380	392	491	503	509	515	521	527	539
52	79	85	66	67	73	96	591	618	624	605	606	612	635	346	373	379	360	361	367	390	493	520	526	507	508	514	537
92	71	72	78	84	65	56	631	610	611	617	623	604	595	386	365	366	372	378	359	350	533	512	513	519	525	506	497
90	83	64	70	76	77	58	629	622	603	609	615	616	597	384	377	358	364	370	371	352	531	524	505	511	517	518	499
88	75	81	82	63	69	60	627	614	620	621	602	608	599	382	369	375	376	357	363	354	529	516	522	523	504	510	501
55	61	59	94	95	97	57	594	600	598	633	634	636	596	349	355	353	388	389	391	351	496	502	500	535	536	538	498
777	773	775	740	739	737	779	140	136	138	103	102	100	142	483	479	481	446	445	443	485	238	234	236	201	200	198	240
736	748	754	760	766	772	784	99	111	117	123	129	135	147	442	454	460	466	472	478	490	197	209	215	221	227	233	245
738	765	771	752	753	759	782	101	128	134	115	116	122	145	444	471	477	458	459	465	488	199	226	232	213	214	220	243
778	757	758	764	770	751	742	141	120	121	127	133	114	105	484	463	464	470	476	457	448	239	218	219	225	231	212	203
776	769	750	756	762	763	744	139	132	113	119	125	126	107	482	475	456	462	468	469	450	237	230	211	217	223	224	205
774	761	767	768	749	755	746	137	124	130	131	112	118	109	480	467	473	474	455	461	452	235	222	228	229	210	216	207
741	747	745	780	781	783	743	104	110	108	143	144	146	106	447	453	451	486	487	489	449	202	208	206	241	242	244	204
434	430	432	397	396	394	436	287	283	285	250	249	247	289	728	724	726	691	690	688	730	189	185	187	152	151	149	191
393	405	411	417	423	429	441	246	258	264	270	276	282	294	687	699	705	711	717	723	735	148	160	166	172	178	184	196
395	422	428	409	410	416	439	248	275	281	262	263	269	292	689	716	722	703	704	710	733	150	177	183	164	165	171	194
435	414	415	421	427	408	399	288	267	268	274	280	261	252	729	708	709	715	721	702	693	190	169	170	176	182	163	154
433	426	407	413	419	420	401	286	279	260	266	272	273	254	727	720	701	707	713	714	695	188	181	162	168	174	175	156
431	418	424	425	406	412	403	284	271	277	278	259	265	256	725	712	718	719	700	706	697	186	173	179	180	161	167	158
398	404	402	437	438	440	400	251	257	255	290	291	293	253	692	698	696	731	732	734	694	153	159	157	192	193	195	155

It is formed by blocks of *bordered* magic squares of order 9 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 7 are *pandiagonal* with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{28 \times 28} := 10990$.

3.7 Magic Square of Order 30

In this case we shall use *bordered* magic square of order 5 given in Example 1 to write *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 30.

Example 27. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 30 is given by*

22	25	5	7	6	872	875	855	857	856	847	850	830	832	831	822	825	805	807	806	47	50	30	32	31	147	150	130	132	131
2	12	17	10	24	852	862	867	860	874	827	837	842	835	849	802	812	817	810	824	27	37	42	35	49	127	137	142	135	149
3	11	13	15	23	853	861	863	865	873	828	836	838	840	848	803	811	813	815	823	28	36	38	40	48	128	136	138	140	148
18	16	9	14	8	868	866	859	864	858	843	841	834	839	833	818	816	809	814	808	43	41	34	39	33	143	141	134	139	133
20	1	21	19	4	870	851	871	869	854	845	826	846	844	829	820	801	821	819	804	45	26	46	44	29	145	126	146	144	129
747	750	730	732	731	197	200	180	182	181	697	700	680	682	681	222	225	205	207	206	272	275	255	257	256	622	625	605	607	606
727	737	742	735	749	177	187	192	185	199	677	687	692	685	699	202	212	217	210	224	252	262	267	260	274	602	612	617	610	624
728	736	738	740	748	178	186	188	190	198	678	686	688	690	698	203	211	213	215	223	253	261	263	265	273	603	611	613	615	623
743	741	734	739	733	193	191	184	189	183	693	691	684	689	683	218	216	209	214	208	268	266	259	264	258	618	616	609	614	608
745	726	746	744	729	195	176	196	194	179	695	676	696	694	679	220	201	221	219	204	270	251	271	269	254	620	601	621	619	604
597	600	580	582	581	572	575	555	557	556	372	375	355	357	356	397	400	380	382	381	497	500	480	482	481	322	325	305	307	306
577	587	592	585	599	552	562	567	560	574	352	362	367	360	374	377	387	392	385	399	477	487	492	485	499	302	312	317	310	324
578	586	588	590	598	553	561	563	565	573	353	361	363	365	373	378	386	388	390	398	478	486	488	490	498	303	311	313	315	323
593	591	584	589	583	568	566	559	564	558	368	366	359	364	358	393	391	384	389	383	493	491	484	489	483	318	316	309	314	308
595	576	596	594	579	570	551	571	569	554	370	351	371	369	354	395	376	396	394	379	495	476	496	494	479	320	301	321	319	304
447	450	430	432	431	347	350	330	332	331	522	525	505	507	506	547	550	530	532	531	422	425	405	407	406	472	475	455	457	456
427	437	442	435	449	327	337	342	335	349	502	512	517	510	524	527	537	542	535	549	402	412	417	410	424	452	462	467	460	474
428	436	438	440	448	328	336	338	340	348	503	511	513	515	523	528	536	538	540	548	403	411	413	415	423	453	461	463	465	473
443	441	434	439	433	343	341	334	339	333	518	516	509	514	508	543	541	534	539	533	418	416	409	414	408	468	466	459	464	458
445	426	446	444	429	345	326	346	344	329	520	501	521	519	504	545	526	546	544	529	420	401	421	419	404	470	451	471	469	454
172	175	155	157	156	647	650	630	632	631	247	250	230	232	231	672	675	655	657	656	722	725	705	707	706	297	300	280	282	281
152	162	167	160	174	627	637	642	635	649	227	237	242	235	249	652	662	667	660	674	702	712	717	710	724	277	287	292	285	299
153	161	163	165	173	628	636	638	640	648	228	236	238	240	248	653	661	663	665	673	703	711	713	715	723	278	286	288	290	298
168	166	159	164	158	643	641	634	639	633	243	241	234	239	233	668	666	659	664	658	718	716	709	714	708	293	291	284	289	283
170	151	171	169	154	645	626	646	644	629	245	226	246	244	229	670	651	671	669	654	720	701	721	719	704	295	276	296	294	279
772	775	755	757	756	122	125	105	107	106	72	75	55	57	56	97	100	80	82	81	797	800	780	782	781	897	900	880	882	881
752	762	767	760	774	102	112	117	110	124	52	62	67	60	74	77	87	92	85	99	777	787	792	785	799	877	887	892	885	899
753	761	763	765	773	103	111	113	115	123	53	61	63	65	73	78	86	88	90	98	778	786	788	790	798	878	886	888	890	898
768	766	759	764	758	118	116	109	114	108	68	66	59	64	58	93	91	84	89	83	793	791	784	789	783	893	891	884	889	883
770	751	771	769	754	120	101	121	119	104	70	51	71	69	54	95	76	96	94	79	795	776	796	794	779	895	876	896	894	879

*It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 5 with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{30 \times 30} := 13515$.*

3.8 Magic Squares of Order 33

In this case we shall use **bordered** and **block-bordered** magic squares of order 7 given in Examples 2 and 3 to write **block-wise bordered** magic squares of order 33.

Example 28. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 33 is given by*

375	383	381	379	377	476	477	479	481	483	373	980	988	986	984	982	1081	1082	1084	1086	1088	978	133	141	139	137	135	234	235	237	239	241	131
484	391	463	461	459	458	395	397	399	393	364	1089	996	1068	1066	1064	1063	1000	1002	1004	998	969	242	149	221	219	217	216	153	155	157	151	122
482	384	441	437	439	404	403	401	443	464	366	1087	989	1046	1042	1044	1009	1008	1006	1048	1069	971	240	142	199	195	197	162	161	159	201	222	124
480	386	400	433	436	416	418	417	448	462	368	1085	991	1005	1038	1041	1021	1023	1022	1053	1067	973	238	144	158	191	194	174	176	175	206	220	126
478	388	402	413	423	428	421	435	446	460	370	1083	993	1007	1018	1028	1033	1026	1040	1051	1065	975	236	146	160	171	181	186	179	193	204	218	128
374	456	442	414	422	424	426	434	406	392	474	979	1061	1047	1019	1027	1029	1031	1039	1011	997	1079	132	214	200	172	180	182	184	192	164	150	232
376	454	440	429	427	420	425	419	408	394	472	981	1059	1045	1034	1032	1025	1030	1024	1013	999	1077	134	212	198	187	185	178	183	177	166	152	230
378	452	438	431	412	432	430	415	410	396	470	983	1057	1043	1036	1017	1037	1035	1020	1015	1001	1075	136	210	196	189	170	190	188	173	168	154	228
380	450	405	411	409	444	445	447	407	398	468	985	1055	1010	1016	1014	1049	1050	1052	1012	1003	1073	138	208	163	169	167	202	203	205	165	156	226
382	455	385	387	389	390	453	451	449	457	466	987	1060	990	992	994	995	1058	1056	1054	1062	1071	140	213	143	145	147	148	211	209	207	215	224
475	465	467	469	471	372	371	369	367	365	473	1080	1070	1072	1074	1076	977	976	974	972	970	1078	233	223	225	227	229	130	129	127	125	123	231
254	262	260	258	256	355	356	358	360	362	252	496	504	502	500	498	597	598	600	602	604	494	738	746	744	742	740	839	840	842	844	846	736
363	270	342	340	338	337	274	276	278	272	243	605	512	584	582	580	579	516	518	520	514	485	847	754	826	824	822	821	758	760	762	756	727
361	263	320	316	318	283	282	280	322	343	245	603	505	562	558	560	525	524	522	564	585	487	845	747	804	800	802	767	766	764	806	827	729
359	265	279	312	315	295	297	296	327	341	247	601	507	521	554	557	537	539	538	569	583	489	843	749	763	796	799	779	781	780	811	825	731
357	267	281	292	302	307	300	314	325	339	249	599	509	523	534	544	549	542	556	567	581	491	841	751	765	776	786	791	784	798	809	823	733
253	335	321	293	301	303	305	313	285	271	353	495	577	563	535	543	545	547	555	527	513	595	737	819	805	777	785	787	789	797	769	755	837
255	333	319	308	306	299	304	298	287	273	351	497	575	561	550	548	541	546	540	529	515	593	739	817	803	792	790	783	788	782	771	757	835
257	331	317	310	291	311	309	294	289	275	349	499	573	559	552	533	553	551	536	531	517	591	741	815	801	794	775	795	793	778	773	759	833
259	329	284	290	288	323	324	326	286	277	347	501	571	526	532	530	565	566	568	528	519	589	743	813	768	774	772	807	808	810	770	761	831
261	334	264	266	268	269	332	330	328	336	345	503	576	506	508	510	511	574	572	570	578	587	745	818	748	750	752	753	816	814	812	820	829
354	344	346	348	350	251	250	248	246	244	352	596	586	588	590	592	493	492	490	488	486	594	838	828	830	832	834	735	734	732	730	728	836
859	867	865	863	861	960	961	963	965	967	857	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	617	625	623	621	619	718	719	721	723	725	615
968	875	947	945	943	942	879	881	883	877	848	121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	726	633	705	703	701	700	637	639	641	635	606
966	868	925	921	923	888	887	885	927	948	850	119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	724	626	683	679	681	646	645	643	685	706	608
964	870	884	917	920	900	902	901	932	946	852	117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	722	628	642	675	678	658	660	659	690	704	610
962	872	886	897	907	912	905	919	930	944	854	115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	720	630	644	655	665	670	663	677	688	702	612
858	940	926	898	906	908	910	918	890	876	958	11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	616	698	684	656	664	666	668	676	648	634	716
860	938	924	913	911	904	909	903	892	878	956	13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	618	696	682	671	669	662	667	661	650	636	714
862	936	922	915	896	916	914	899	894	880	954	15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	620	694	680	673	654	674	672	657	652	638	712
864	934	889	895	893	928	929	931	891	882	952	17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	622	692	647	653	651	686	687	689	649	640	710
866	939	869	871	873	874	937	935	933	941	950	19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	624	697	627	629	631	632	695	693	691	699	708
959	949	951	953	955	856	855	853	851	849	957	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	717	707	709	711	713	614	613	611	609	607	715

It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 11 with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{33 \times 33} := 17985$.

Example 29. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 33 with inner block of order 7 is given by*

375	383	381	379	377	476	477	479	481	483	373	980	988	986	984	982	1081	1082	1084	1086	1088	978	133	141	139	137	135	234	235	237	239	241	131
484	391	463	461	459	458	395	397	399	393	364	1089	996	1068	1066	1064	1063	1000	1002	1004	998	969	242	149	221	219	217	216	153	155	157	151	122
482	384	400	408	416	424	432	440	448	464	366	1087	989	1005	1013	1021	1029	1037	1045	1053	1069	971	240	142	158	166	174	182	190	198	206	222	124
480	386	439	447	406	407	415	423	431	462	368	1085	991	1044	1052	1011	1012	1020	1028	1036	1067	973	238	144	197	205	164	165	173	181	189	220	126
478	388	422	430	438	446	405	413	414	460	370	1083	993	1027	1035	1043	1051	1010	1018	1019	1065	975	236	146	180	188	196	204	163	171	172	218	128
374	456	412	420	421	429	437	445	404	392	474	979	1061	1017	1025	1026	1034	1042	1050	1009	997	1079	132	214	170	178	179	187	195	203	162	150	232
376	454	444	403	411	419	427	428	436	394	472	981	1059	1049	1008	1016	1024	1032	1033	1041	999	1077	134	212	202	161	169	177	185	186	194	152	230
378	452	434	435	443	402	410	418	426	396	470	983	1057	1039	1040	1048	1007	1015	1023	1031	1001	1075	136	210	192	193	201	160	168	176	184	154	228
380	450	417	425	433	441	442	401	409	398	468	985	1055	1022	1030	1038	1046	1047	1006	1014	1003	1073	138	208	175	183	191	199	200	159	167	156	226
382	455	385	387	389	390	453	451	449	457	466	987	1060	990	992	994	995	1058	1056	1054	1062	1071	140	213	143	145	147	148	211	209	207	215	224
475	465	467	469	471	372	371	369	367	365	473	1080	1070	1072	1074	1076	977	976	974	972	970	1078	233	223	225	227	229	130	129	127	125	123	231
254	262	260	258	256	355	356	358	360	362	252	496	504	502	500	498	597	598	600	602	604	494	738	746	744	742	740	839	840	842	844	846	736
363	270	342	340	338	337	274	276	278	272	243	605	512	584	582	580	579	516	518	520	514	485	847	754	826	824	822	821	758	760	762	756	727
361	263	279	287	295	303	311	319	327	343	245	603	505	521	529	537	545	553	561	569	585	487	845	747	763	771	779	787	795	803	811	827	729
359	265	318	326	285	286	294	302	310	341	247	601	507	560	568	527	528	536	544	552	583	489	843	749	802	810	769	770	778	786	794	825	731
357	267	301	309	317	325	284	292	293	339	249	599	509	543	551	559	567	526	534	535	581	491	841	751	785	793	801	809	768	776	777	823	733
253	335	291	299	300	308	316	324	283	271	353	495	577	533	541	542	550	558	566	525	513	595	737	819	775	783	784	792	800	808	767	755	837
255	333	323	282	290	298	306	307	315	273	351	497	575	565	524	532	540	548	549	557	515	593	739	817	807	766	774	782	790	791	799	757	835
257	331	313	314	322	281	289	297	305	275	349	499	573	555	556	564	523	531	539	547	517	591	741	815	797	798	806	765	773	781	789	759	833
259	329	296	304	312	320	321	280	288	277	347	501	571	538	546	554	562	563	522	530	519	589	743	813	780	788	796	804	805	764	772	761	831
261	334	264	266	268	269	332	330	328	336	345	503	576	506	508	510	511	574	572	570	578	587	745	818	748	750	752	753	816	814	812	820	829
354	344	346	348	350	251	250	248	246	244	352	596	586	588	590	592	493	492	490	488	486	594	838	828	830	832	834	735	734	732	730	728	836
859	867	865	863	861	960	961	963	965	967	857	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	617	625	623	621	619	718	719	721	723	725	615
968	875	947	945	943	942	879	881	883	877	848	121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	726	633	705	703	701	700	637	639	641	635	606
966	868	884	892	900	908	916	924	932	948	850	119	21	37	45	53	61	69	77	85	101	3	724	626	642	650	658	666	674	682	690	706	608
964	870	923	931	890	891	899	907	915	946	852	117	23	76	84	43	44	52	60	68	99	5	722	628	681	689	648	649	657	665	673	704	610
962	872	906	914	922	930	889	897	898	944	854	115	25	59	67	75	83	42	50	51	97	7	720	630	664	672	680	688	647	655	656	702	612
858	940	896	904	905	913	921	929	888	876	958	11	93	49	57	58	66	74	82	41	29	111	616	698	654	662	663	671	679	687	646	634	716
860	938	928	887	895	903	911	912	920	878	956	13	91	81	40	48	56	64	65	73	31	109	618	696	686	645	653	661	669	670	678	636	714
862	936	918	919	927	886	894	902	910	880	954	15	89	71	72	80	39	47	55	63	33	107	620	694	676	677	685	644	652	660	668	638	712
864	934	901	909	917	925	926	885	893	882	952	17	87	54	62	70	78	79	38	46	35	105	622	692	659	667	675	683	684	643	651	640	710
866	939	869	871	873	874	937	935	933	941	950	19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	624	697	627	629	631	632	695	693	691	699	708
959	949	951	953	955	856	855	853	851	849	957	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	717	707	709	711	713	614	613	611	609	607	715

*It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 11 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 7 are **pandiagonal** with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{33 \times 33} := 17985$.*

Example 30. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 33 with inner blocks of order 3 is given by*

375	383	381	379	377	476	477	479	481	483	373	980	988	986	984	982	1081	1082	1084	1086	1088	978	133	141	139	137	135	234	235	237	239	241	131
484	405	454	413	410	447	415	403	452	417	364	1089	1010	1059	1018	1015	1052	1020	1008	1057	1022	969	242	163	212	171	168	205	173	161	210	175	122
482	418	404	450	411	406	455	416	408	448	366	1087	1023	1009	1055	1016	1011	1060	1021	1013	1053	971	240	176	162	208	169	164	213	174	166	206	124
480	449	414	409	451	419	402	453	412	407	368	1085	1054	1019	1014	1056	1024	1007	1058	1017	1012	973	238	207	172	167	209	177	160	211	170	165	126
478	423	391	458	428	384	460	421	389	462	370	1083	1028	996	1063	1033	989	1065	1026	994	1067	975	236	181	149	216	186	142	218	179	147	220	128
374	463	422	387	456	424	392	461	426	385	474	979	1068	1027	992	1061	1029	997	1066	1031	990	1079	132	221	180	145	214	182	150	219	184	143	232
376	386	459	427	388	464	420	390	457	425	472	981	991	1064	1032	993	1069	1025	995	1062	1030	1077	134	144	217	185	146	222	178	148	215	183	230
378	441	436	395	446	429	397	439	434	399	470	983	1046	1041	1000	1051	1034	1002	1044	1039	1004	1075	136	199	194	153	204	187	155	197	192	157	228
380	400	440	432	393	442	437	398	444	430	468	985	1005	1045	1037	998	1047	1042	1003	1049	1035	1073	138	158	198	190	151	200	195	156	202	188	226
382	431	396	445	433	401	438	435	394	443	466	987	1036	1001	1050	1038	1006	1043	1040	999	1048	1071	140	189	154	203	191	159	196	193	152	201	224
475	465	467	469	471	372	371	369	367	365	473	1080	1070	1072	1074	1076	977	976	974	972	970	1078	233	223	225	227	229	130	129	127	125	123	231
254	262	260	258	256	355	356	358	360	362	252	496	504	502	500	498	597	598	600	602	604	494	738	746	744	742	740	839	840	842	844	846	736
363	284	333	292	289	326	294	282	331	296	243	605	526	575	534	531	568	536	524	573	538	485	847	768	817	776	773	810	778	766	815	780	727
361	297	283	329	290	285	334	295	287	327	245	603	539	525	571	532	527	576	537	529	569	487	845	781	767	813	774	769	818	779	771	811	729
359	328	293	288	330	298	281	332	291	286	247	601	570	535	530	572	540	523	574	533	528	489	843	812	777	772	814	782	765	816	775	770	731
357	302	270	337	307	263	339	300	268	341	249	599	544	512	579	549	505	581	542	510	583	491	841	786	754	821	791	747	823	784	752	825	733
253	342	301	266	335	303	271	340	305	264	353	495	584	543	508	577	545	513	582	547	506	595	737	826	785	750	819	787	755	824	789	748	837
255	265	338	306	267	343	299	269	336	304	351	497	507	580	548	509	585	541	511	578	546	593	739	749	822	790	751	827	783	753	820	788	835
257	320	315	274	325	308	276	318	313	278	349	499	562	557	516	567	550	518	560	555	520	591	741	804	799	758	809	792	760	802	797	762	833
259	279	319	311	272	321	316	277	323	309	347	501	521	561	553	514	563	558	519	565	551	589	743	763	803	795	756	805	800	761	807	793	831
261	310	275	324	312	280	317	314	273	322	345	503	552	517	566	554	522	559	556	515	564	587	745	794	759	808	796	764	801	798	757	806	829
354	344	346	348	350	251	250	248	246	244	352	596	586	588	590	592	493	492	490	488	486	594	838	828	830	832	834	735	734	732	730	728	836
859	867	865	863	861	960	961	963	965	967	857	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	617	625	623	621	619	718	719	721	723	725	615
968	889	938	897	894	931	899	887	936	901	848	121	42	91	50	47	84	52	40	89	54	1	726	647	696	655	652	689	657	645	694	659	606
966	902	888	934	895	890	939	900	892	932	850	119	55	41	87	48	43	92	53	45	85	3	724	660	646	692	653	648	697	658	650	690	608
964	933	898	893	935	903	886	937	896	891	852	117	86	51	46	88	56	39	90	49	44	5	722	691	656	651	693	661	644	695	654	649	610
962	907	875	942	912	868	944	905	873	946	854	115	60	28	95	65	21	97	58	26	99	7	720	665	633	700	670	626	702	663	631	704	612
858	947	906	871	940	908	876	945	910	869	958	11	100	59	24	93	61	29	98	63	22	111	616	705	664	629	698	666	634	703	668	627	716
860	870	943	911	872	948	904	874	941	909	956	13	23	96	64	25	101	57	27	94	62	109	618	628	701	669	630	706	662	632	699	667	714
862	925	920	879	930	913	881	923	918	883	954	15	78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	107	620	683	678	637	688	671	639	681	676	641	712
864	884	924	916	877	926	921	882	928	914	952	17	37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	105	622	642	682	674	635	684	679	640	686	672	710
866	915	880	929	917	885	922	919	878	927	950	19	68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	103	624	673	638	687	675	643	680	677	636	685	708
959	949	951	953	955	856	855	853	851	849	957	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	717	707	709	711	713	614	613	611	609	607	715

It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 11 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 9 are **pandiagonal**

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{33 \times 33} := 17985$. Moreover, in each case the blocks of order 3 are *semi-magic* squares of order 3 with equal *semi-magic* sums.

Example 31. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 33 with inner blocks of order 3 is given by*

375	383	381	379	377	476	477	479	481	483	373	980	988	986	984	982	1081	1082	1084	1086	1088	978	133	141	139	137	135	234	235	237	239	241	131
484	384	401	406	418	423	431	443	448	462	364	1089	989	1006	1011	1023	1028	1036	1048	1053	1067	969	242	142	159	164	176	181	189	201	206	220	122
482	416	421	435	438	455	460	391	396	404	366	1087	1021	1026	1040	1043	1060	1065	996	1001	1009	971	240	174	179	193	196	213	218	149	154	162	124
480	445	450	458	389	394	408	411	428	433	368	1085	1050	1055	1063	994	999	1013	1016	1033	1038	973	238	203	208	216	147	152	166	169	186	191	126
478	410	388	393	432	413	427	457	444	452	370	1083	1015	993	998	1037	1018	1032	1062	1049	1057	975	236	168	146	151	190	171	185	215	202	210	128
374	430	417	425	464	442	447	405	386	400	474	979	1035	1022	1030	1069	1047	1052	1010	991	1005	1079	132	188	175	183	222	200	205	163	144	158	232
376	459	440	454	403	390	398	437	415	420	472	981	1064	1045	1059	1008	995	1003	1042	1020	1025	1077	134	217	198	212	161	148	156	195	173	178	230
378	397	402	392	422	436	414	453	461	439	470	983	1002	1007	997	1027	1041	1019	1058	1066	1044	1075	136	155	160	150	180	194	172	211	219	197	228
380	426	434	412	451	456	446	395	409	387	468	985	1031	1039	1017	1056	1061	1051	1000	1014	992	1073	138	184	192	170	209	214	204	153	167	145	226
382	449	463	441	399	407	385	424	429	419	466	987	1054	1068	1046	1004	1012	990	1029	1034	1024	1071	140	207	221	199	157	165	143	182	187	177	224
475	465	467	469	471	372	371	369	367	365	473	1080	1070	1072	1074	1076	977	976	974	972	970	1078	233	223	225	227	229	130	129	127	125	123	231
254	262	260	258	256	355	356	358	360	362	252	496	504	502	500	498	597	598	600	602	604	494	738	746	744	742	740	839	840	842	844	846	736
363	263	280	285	297	302	310	322	327	341	243	605	505	522	527	539	544	552	564	569	583	485	847	747	764	769	781	786	794	806	811	825	727
361	295	300	314	317	334	339	270	275	283	245	603	537	542	556	559	576	581	512	517	525	487	845	779	784	798	801	818	823	754	759	767	729
359	324	329	337	268	273	287	290	307	312	247	601	566	571	579	510	515	529	532	549	554	489	843	808	813	821	752	757	771	774	791	796	731
357	289	267	272	311	292	306	336	323	331	249	599	531	509	514	553	534	548	578	565	573	491	841	773	751	756	795	776	790	820	807	815	733
253	309	296	304	343	321	326	284	265	279	353	495	551	538	546	585	563	568	526	507	521	595	737	793	780	788	827	805	810	768	749	763	837
255	338	319	333	282	269	277	316	294	299	351	497	580	561	575	524	511	519	558	536	541	593	739	822	803	817	766	753	761	800	778	783	835
257	276	281	271	301	315	293	332	340	318	349	499	518	523	513	543	557	535	574	582	560	591	741	760	765	755	785	799	777	816	824	802	833
259	305	313	291	330	335	325	274	288	266	347	501	547	555	533	572	577	567	516	530	508	589	743	789	797	775	814	819	809	758	772	750	831
261	328	342	320	278	286	264	303	308	298	345	503	570	584	562	520	528	506	545	550	540	587	745	812	826	804	762	770	748	787	792	782	829
354	344	346	348	350	251	250	248	246	244	352	596	586	588	590	592	493	492	490	488	486	594	838	828	830	832	834	735	734	732	730	728	836
859	867	865	863	861	960	961	963	965	967	857	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	617	625	623	621	619	718	719	721	723	725	615
968	868	885	890	902	907	915	927	932	946	848	121	21	38	43	55	60	68	80	85	99	1	726	626	643	648	660	665	673	685	690	704	606
966	900	905	919	922	939	944	875	880	888	850	119	53	58	72	75	92	97	28	33	41	3	724	658	663	677	680	697	702	633	638	646	608
964	929	934	942	873	878	892	895	912	917	852	117	82	87	95	26	31	45	48	65	70	5	722	687	692	700	631	636	650	653	670	675	610
962	894	872	877	916	897	911	941	928	936	854	115	47	25	30	69	50	64	94	81	89	7	720	652	630	635	674	655	669	699	686	694	612
858	914	901	909	948	926	931	889	870	884	958	11	67	54	62	101	79	84	42	23	37	111	616	672	659	667	706	684	689	647	628	642	716
860	943	924	938	887	874	882	921	899	904	956	13	96	77	91	40	27	35	74	52	57	109	618	701	682	696	645	632	640	679	657	662	714
862	881	886	876	906	920	898	937	945	923	954	15	34	39	29	59	73	51	90	98	76	107	620	639	644	634	664	678	656	695	703	681	712
864	910	918	896	935	940	930	879	893	871	952	17	63	71	49	88	93	83	32	46	24	105	622	668	676	654	693	698	688	637	651	629	710
866	933	947	925	883	891	869	908	913	903	950	19	86	100	78	36	44	22	61	66	56	103	624	691	705	683	641	649	627	666	671	661	708
959	949	951	953	955	856	855	853	851	849	957	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	717	707	709	711	713	614	613	611	609	607	715

It is formed by blocks of bordered magic squares of order 11 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 9 are bimagic

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{33 \times 33} := 17985$. Moreover, in each case the sum of 9 entries of each block of order 3 are the same as of magic sum of order 9.

3.9 Magic Squares of Order 35

In this case we shall use **bordered** magic square of orders 5 and 7 given in Examples 1 and 2 to write **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 35.

3.9.1 Multiple of 5

Example 32. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 35 is given by*

3.9.2 Multiple of 7

Example 33. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 35 of is given by*

*It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 7 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 5 are **pandiagonal** with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{35 \times 35} := 21455$.*

3.10 Magic Squares of Order 36

In this case we shall use **bordered** magic squares of order 9 given in Examples 4 and 5 to write **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 36.

Example 35. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 36 is given by*

*It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 9 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 7 are **pandiagonal** with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{36 \times 36} := 23346$.*

3.11 Magic Squares of Order 39

In this case we shall use **bordered** and **block-bordered** magic squares of order 13 given in Examples 10, 11, 12 and 13 to write **block-wise bordered** magic squares of order 39.

Example 37. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 39 is given by*

*It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 13 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 7 are **pandiagonal** with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{39 \times 39} := 29679$.*

Example 39. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 39 with inner blocks of order 3 is given by*

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{39 \times 39} := 29679$. Moreover, in each case the blocks of order 3 are *semi-magic* squares of order 3 with equal *semi-magic* sums.

Example 40. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 39 with inner blocks of order 3 is given by*

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{39 \times 39} := 29679$. Moreover, in each case the sum of 9 entries of each block of order 3 are the same as of magic sum of order 9.

3.12 Magic Square of Order 40

Example 41. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 40 is given by*

3.13 Magic Squares of Order 42

Example 42. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 42 is given by*

*It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 7 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 5 are **pandiagonal** with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{42 \times 42} := 37065$.*

3.14 Magic Squares of Order 44

In this case we shall use **bordered** and **block-bordered** magic squares of order 11 given in Examples 6, 7, 8, and ?? to write **block-wise bordered** magic squares of order 44.

Example 44. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 44 is given by*

*It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 11 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 7 are **pandiagonal** with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{44 \times 44} := 42614$.*

Example 46. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 44 with inner blocks of order 3 is given by*

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{44 \times 44} := 42614$. Moreover, in each case the blocks of order 3 are *semi-magic* squares of order 3 with equal *semi-magic* sums.

Example 47. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 33 with inner blocks of order 3 is given by*

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{44 \times 44} := 42614$. Moreover, in each case the sum of 9 entries of each block of order 3 are the same as of magic sum of order 9.

3.15 Magic Squares of Order 45

3.15.1 Multiple of 5

In this case we shall use **bordered** and **block-bordered** magic squares of order 5, 9 and 15 given in Examples 1, 4, 5, 14, 15, 16, and 17 to write **block-wise bordered** magic squares of order 45.

Example 48. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 45 is given by*

equal *semi-magic* sums. The final sum is $S_{45 \times 45} := 45585$.

3.15.2 Multiple of 9

Example 49. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 45 with inner block of order 7 is given by*

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{45 \times 45} := 45585$.

3.15.3 Multiple of 15

Example 51. *block-wise bordered magic square of order 45 is given by*

*It is formed by blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 15 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 7 are **pandiagonal** with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{45 \times 45} := 45585$.*

Example 53. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 45 with inner blocks of order 3 is given by*

885	874	876	878	880	882	884	886	888	890	892	894	896	898	900	902	904	906	908	910	912	914	916	918	920	922	924	926	928	930	932	934	936	938	940	942	944	946	948	950	952	954	956	958	960	962	964	966	968	970	972	974	976	978	980	982	984	986	988	990	992	994	996	998	1000	1002	1004	1006	1008	1010	1012	1014	1016	1018	1020	1022	1024	1026	1028	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1044	1046	1048	1050	1052	1054	1056	1058	1060	1062	1064	1066	1068	1070	1072	1074	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1108	1110	1112	1114	1116	1118	1120	1122	1124	1126	1128	1130	1132	1134	1136	1138	1140	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	1156	1158	1160	1162	1164	1166	1168	1170	1172	1174	1176	1178	1180	1182	1184	1186	1188	1190	1192	1194	1196	1198	1200	1202	1204	1206	1208	1210	1212	1214	1216	1218	1220	1222	1224	1226	1228	1230	1232	1234	1236	1238	1240	1242	1244	1246	1248	1250	1252	1254	1256	1258	1260	1262	1264	1266	1268	1270	1272	1274	1276	1278	1280	1282	1284	1286	1288	1290	1292	1294	1296	1298	1300	1302	1304	1306	1308	1310	1312	1314	1316	1318	1320	1322	1324	1326	1328	1330	1332	1334	1336	1338	1340	1342	1344	1346	1348	1350	1352	1354	1356	1358	1360	1362	1364	1366	1368	1370	1372	1374	1376	1378	1380	1382	1384	1386	1388	1390	1392	1394	1396	1398	1400	1402	1404	1406	1408	1410	1412	1414	1416	1418	1420	1422	1424	1426	1428	1430	1432	1434	1436	1438	1440	1442	1444	1446	1448	1450	1452	1454	1456	1458	1460	1462	1464	1466	1468	1470	1472	1474	1476	1478	1480	1482	1484	1486	1488	1490	1492	1494	1496	1498	1500	1502	1504	1506	1508	1510	1512	1514	1516	1518	1520	1522	1524	1526	1528	1530	1532	1534	1536	1538	1540	1542	1544	1546	1548	1550	1552	1554	1556	1558	1560	1562	1564	1566	1568	1570	1572	1574	1576	1578	1580	1582	1584	1586	1588	1590	1592	1594	1596	1598	1600	1602	1604	1606	1608	1610	1612	1614	1616	1618	1620	1622	1624	1626	1628	1630	1632	1634	1636	1638	1640	1642	1644	1646	1648	1650	1652	1654	1656	1658	1660	1662	1664	1666	1668	1670	1672	1674	1676	1678	1680	1682	1684	1686	1688	1690	1692	1694	1696	1698	1700	1702	1704	1706	1708	1710	1712	1714	1716	1718	1720	1722	1724	1726	1728	1730	1732	1734	1736	1738	1740	1742	1744	1746	1748	1750	1752	1754	1756	1758	1760	1762	1764	1766	1768	1770	1772	1774	1776	1778	1780	1782	1784	1786	1788	1790	1792	1794	1796	1798	1800	1802	1804	1806	1808	1810	1812	1814	1816	1818	1820	1822	1824	1826	1828	1830	1832	1834	1836	1838	1840	1842	1844	1846	1848	1850	1852	1854	1856	1858	1860	1862	1864	1866	1868	1870	1872	1874	1876	1878	1880	1882	1884	1886	1888	1890	1892	1894	1896	1898	1900	1902	1904	1906	1908	1910	1912	1914	1916	1918	1920	1922	1924	1926	1928	1930	1932	1934	1936	1938	1940	1942	1944	1946	1948	1950	1952	1954	1956	1958	1960	1962	1964	1966	1968	1970	1972	1974	1976	1978	1980	1982	1984	1986	1988	1990	1992	1994	1996	1998	2000	2002	2004	2006	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016	2018	2020	2022	2024	2026	2028	2030	2032	2034	2036	2038	2040	2042	2044	2046	2048	2050	2052	2054	2056	2058	2060	2062	2064	2066	2068	2070	2072	2074	2076	2078	2080	2082	2084	2086	2088	2090	2092	2094	2096	2098	2100	2102	2104	2106	2108	2110	2112	2114	2116	2118	2120	2122	2124	2126	2128	2130	2132	2134	2136	2138	2140	2142	2144	2146	2148	2150	2152	2154	2156	2158	2160	2162	2164	2166	2168	2170	2172	2174	2176	2178	2180	2182	2184	2186	2188	2190	2192	2194	2196	2198	2200	2202	2204	2206	2208	2210	2212	2214	2216	2218	2220	2222	2224	2226	2228	2230	2232	2234	2236	2238	2240	2242	2244	2246	2248	2250	2252	2254	2256	2258	2260	2262	2264	2266	2268	2270	2272	2274	2276	2278	2280	2282	2284	2286	2288	2290	2292	2294	2296	2298	2300	2302	2304	2306	2308	2310	2312	2314	2316	2318	2320	2322	2324	2326	2328	2330	2332	2334	2336	2338	2340	2342	2344	2346	2348	2350	2352	2354	2356	2358	2360	2362	2364	2366	2368	2370	2372	2374	2376	2378	2380	2382	2384	2386	2388	2390	2392	2394	2396	2398	2400
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It is formed by blocks of bordered magic squares of order 15 with different magic sums. The inner magic squares of order 9 are pandiagonal

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{45 \times 45} := 45585$. Moreover, in each case the blocks of order 3 are *semi-magic* squares of order 3 with equal *semi-magic* sums.

Example 54. *block-wise block-bordered magic square of order 45 with inner blocks of order 3 is given by*

with different magic sums. The final sum is $S_{45 \times 45} := 45585$. Moreover, in each case the sum of 9 entries of each block of order 3 are the same as of magic sum of order 9.

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4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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[4] H. White, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/SODLS.html>

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● Block-Bordered Magic Squares

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